

IR36-derived lines are stable high yielders in Kerala, India

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IR36 was used in a rice breeding program at Pattambi to develop varieties with multiple resistance to pests and high adaptability. Six short-duration, semidwarf lines evolving from this program were evaluated with IR36 and popular high-yielding variety Jyothi for grain yield and other agronomic attributes.

Experiments were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Tests were conducted in different seasons including 1987, 1988, and 1989 kharif (monsoon); 1989 and 1991 summer; and 1990 rabi (wet). Plots were 10 m² and spacing was 15 × 10 cm. Recommended agronomic and plant protection measures were followed. Grain yields were recorded at 14% moisture level. Stability of the genotypes over six environments was analyzed.

Regression of genotypes for average yield on the environmental index resulted in regression coefficients (bi) from 0.88 to 1.34. Deviation from regression mean squares (*s²d*) ranged from -0.05 to 0.21 (Table 1). These stability parameters were not significant, indicating that all lines tested were stable yielders across the environments.

Rice cultures KAU8754 and KAU8755 had bi very close to unity (1.04), which indicates their highly stable performance across environments tested. These two cultures and KAU8753 and KAU8756 had grain yields higher than

Table 1. Mean grain yield (t/ha) and estimates of stability parameters for 8 rice genotypes over 6 environments.

Genotype	$\bar{x}$	bi	<i>s²d</i>
KAU8753	4.1	0.93	-0.05
KAU8754	4.1	1.04	0.15
KAU8755	4.1	1.04	0.04
KAU8756	4.4	1.34	0.21
KAU8757	3.7	0.89	0.03
KAU8759	3.9	1.13	0.04
IR36	3.7	0.91	0.05
Jyothi	3.5	0.88	0.07
Av	3.9		

Table 2. Parentage and agronomic attributes of promising rice genotypes from Pattambi, India.

Genotype	Parentage	Duration (d)	Mean plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)
KAU8753	IR36/Jyothi	115	85	5.8
KAU8754	IR36/Jyothi	115	90	5.5
KAU8755	IR36/Pavizham	115	88	3.9
KAU8756	IR36/Pavizham	110	90	6.5
KAU8757	IR36/Cul 23332-2	115	87	5.0
KAU8759	IR36/Annapoorna	100	80	5.1
IR36 (check)		115	90	5.5
Jyothi (check)		115	90	3.9

the pooled mean. KAU8756 yielded the most at 4.4 t/ha and had the highest bi (1.34), indicating this genotype's superior performance under favorable environments. (See Table 2 for parentage and agronomic attributes of genotypes.)

All six genotypes derived from crosses with IR36 were stable yielders in kharif,

rabi, and summer seasons. KAU8753, KAU8754, KAU8755, and KAU8756 are recommended for use in breeding programs aiming to develop cultivars with high yield potential and adaptability. KAU8754 was released recently in Kerala as Kairali (Ptb 49), and KAU8756 as Kanchana (Ptb 50). ■

Wei You 647: a new high-yielding hybrid rice

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Indica/japonica hybrid rice could have stronger heterosis than indica/indica hybrids, but poor seed set is a major problem. By hybridizing an indica restorer line with a japonica variety and backcrossing, an indica-type restorer line (647 R) with japonica characteristics has been developed. Hybrids of 647 R and

indica cytoplasmic male sterile lines V20 A and Zhen Shan 97 A have shown very strong heterosis and high yield ability.

Hybrid Wei You 647 is the F₁ progeny of V20 A/647 R. It was ranked first five times and second twice in various yield trials and recorded a 4.3-13.7% increase in yield over commercial hybrid checks. (See table for yield results in the 1991 China National Hybrid Rice Yield Trial.)

Yield potential of Wei You 647 is high and stable in on-farm cultivation. Wei You 647 has been released for commercial production. ■

Yield performance of top 4 new hybrid rices in the China National Hybrid Rice Yield Trial over 21 locations. China, 1991.

Hybrid	Growth duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield over that of check (%)	Rank
Wei You 647 (V20 A/647 R)	133	7.6	13.7	1
Shan You 20964 (97 A/20964 R)	130	7.4	10.3	2
Wei You 77 (V20 A/77 R)	127	7.1	7.0	3
Shan You 3-9 (97 A/3-9 R)	131	7.1	7.0	4
Wei You 64 (V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R) (check)	127	6.7	-	5